

Title: Building Dynamic Sentiment Analysis Service, (Draft Version 0.1)

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INTRODUCTION:

Using the cutting edge technology in NLP to scrap web contents and applying sentiment analysis to extract trends in business and society popular talks in different languages, after analyzing phase the user can visualize the results using charts.

AIM:

To facilitate the process of sentiment analysis using google chrome extension on any site.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Building a chrome extension which communicate with background up to date multi discipline dictionaries in different languages like: English, French, Spanish, Turkish, Arabic.

RESULTS:

Still on development phase.

CONCLUSIONS:

Still on development phase.

KEYWORDS:

NLP; NLTK; Deep Learning; Languages; Python; Text Mining; Sentiment Analysis;

BIOGRAPHY:

Amr Salama has a graduated from Cairo University 2002 with solid knowledge in Software Development using C++, Java, C#, in many ERP solutions and Web Applications, in 2017 I decided to make a career shift on Artificial Intelligence, Data Science, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, I am focusing my study on NLP and building applications which can innovate multicultural societies.